

Sexual Education. A Challenge for the Romanian School

Lavinia-Elena Olăfnescu

Romania, Iași, Str. Ciurchi nr. 107 A, PhD candidate at Alexandru Ioan Cuza University, Faculty of Philosophy and Social-Political Science

ABSTRACT: The review emphasizes the balanced approach and the topicality of the information in the book "Sexual education. A challenge for the Romanian school" written by Cristina Neamțu. The book explores the complexity and importance of sexuality education, addressing the challenges of adolescence and media impact, in a two-part structure.

The way the book promotes the transmission of information and the development of critical thinking is appreciated. Although published 19 years ago, the review emphasizes that the information remains current and relevant, constituting a valuable resource for those interested in the evolution of sexuality education in Romania. Recommends the book for all those involved in the reform of the sex education system, emphasizing its contribution to improving the quality of life of adolescents in Romanian society.

Cristina NEAMȚU is a PhD associate professor at the Department of Medical Psychology and Special Psychopedagogy of the "Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University in Iasi. His areas of expertise include the analysis of deviant behaviors, forms of psychopedagogical assistance for people with special needs and human sexuality.

The volume *Sexual education. A challenge for the Romanian school* was published in 2005 by the European Institute publishing house, being part of the Universitaria collection.

The present paper is structured in two parts. The first part addresses the issue of sexual education, and the second is centered on the presentation of human sexuality. The first part of the book contains 3 chapters and the second part contains 4 chapters. In total, the volume consists of 7 chapters that address every aspect related to human sexuality.

The paper *Sexual education. A challenge for the Romanian school* written by Cristina Neamțu in 2005 brings into discussion a particularly sensitive and important topic in the context of education: sex education in schools. The author aims to explore not only the theoretical and practical aspects of the implementation of this type of education, but also to analyze the challenges and its impact on students and the education system in Romania.

The volume begins by analyzing the role of the school in the sexual education process, highlighting the status, objectives and implementation methods of this discipline. The author points out that although sex education was not required by law at the time, there was an increased need to address this topic in schools, arguing that it should be an integral part of general education, overcoming the limitations of isolated leadership or biology classes.

Cristina Neamțu highlights the difficulties and complexity of implementing complete sex education in schools. This brings up the challenges that teachers face in conveying correct and relevant information, sometimes being underprepared or embarrassed in front of sensitive topics. The book encourages a broader and more coherent approach to sexuality education in order to respond to students' needs and curiosities in an effective way.

The first part of the book explores the process of sexualization and the formation of sexual identity, with a focus on the specific challenges of adolescence. The author analyzes how sex education can contribute to establishing a healthy framework for the development of young people's sexual identity, emphasizing the importance of a balanced and open informative approach.

Another central theme addressed is sexual health and contraception. The author argues that adequate sex education should provide detailed and accurate information in these areas, thus contributing to the prevention of sexual health problems and the promotion of a responsible attitude among young people.

The book also investigates the commercial exploitation of sexuality and its impact on adolescent perceptions. The author discusses how media and commercial influence can distort young people's understanding of sexuality and how sexuality education can serve as an antidote to these negative influences.

The volume argues that the approach to sexuality education must be balanced and informatively open, to avoid stigmatization or misinformation. By providing accurate and accessible information, sexuality education can play a significant role in raising awareness and promoting a healthy attitude towards one's own sexual identity and that of others.

Sexual Education. A Challenge for The Romanian School

Through the details presented in the second chapter, the book provides a detailed look at how sexuality education can serve as a catalyst for positive personal and social development during the sensitive period of adolescence, contributing to the understanding of physical changes and the psychological and social aspects surrounding identity young people's sexuality.

The fourth and fifth chapters bring to the fore sexual health and the importance of sexual education in promoting it. Explores the process of sexualization and the formation of sexual identity during adolescence. The author analyzes how sex education can positively influence the development of young people's sexual identity. In a period of intense physical and emotional changes, sexuality education becomes an indispensable tool in providing adolescents with a healthy framework to understand and accept sexual diversity.

By addressing topics such as contraception and the prevention of sexually transmitted diseases, the book aims to provide solid knowledge that will contribute to the formation of a responsible attitude towards one's sexual health. Sexual education, the author claims, should not be limited to simple information, but to provide practical tools for adopting healthy and responsible behaviors in the field of sexuality.

The second part of the book is devoted to a detailed presentation of human sexuality. The author takes a scientific and objective perspective, giving readers an in-depth look at sexual diversity. By approaching this subject with scientific rigor, the book aims to demystify taboo aspects and provide accurate and up-to-date information on the variability and complexity of human sexuality. A key concern of the book is to promote open and tolerant understanding of sexual diversity. The author addresses topics such as gender identity and sexual orientation, providing a platform for understanding and accepting diversity in a way that contributes to the development of a more inclusive and respectful society.

Reading *Sex Education. A challenge for the Romanian school*, I was deeply impressed by the balanced approach of the author, Cristina Neamțu, on such a sensitive topic. The volume does not limit itself to technical aspects, but explores in depth the implications and challenges of introducing sexuality education in schools. The arguments were supported by solid evidence and a careful analysis of the situation in the Romanian context.

In addition, I appreciate how the book promotes the transmission of information and the development of critical thinking among students. This approach resonates with the contemporary need to understand and evaluate information in the most balanced and objective way possible, especially in a society marked by rapid flows of information and complex debates. Also, a very important aspect to mention is that although the volume was published 19 years ago, the information provided is still current today, explaining in great detail concepts that are and will always be valid. From my perspective, a good and well-documented book is one that includes information so good that it doesn't need further improvement.

Sex education. A Challenge for the Romanian School offers a detailed foray into the world of sexuality education and its associated challenges in the Romanian school context. The book manages to bring together a diverse range of topics, from legal issues and teaching practices to the complexities of sexual identity formation and the influence of excessive media coverage. The main ideas are carefully structured in each chapter, highlighting the need for a comprehensive and balanced approach to sex education in schools.

I recommend this book to anyone interested in reforming the sex education system. Students will find answers to their questions, parents will benefit from a broader perspective on their children's education, and educators and decision-makers will find this book a valuable resource in the decision-making process. The book not only informs, but also inspires the opening of constructive debates and concrete actions. Therefore, it should not be missing from the library of any reader concerned with the evolution of sexual education in schools and in Romanian society. It is an important contribution to the dialogue about how we can improve the quality of sex education and, implicitly, the quality of life of teenagers in Romania.

REFERENCES

- 1) Neamțu, Cristina (2005). *Sexual education. A challenge for the Romanian school*, European Institute Publishing House, Iași.
- 2) Foucault, Michel (1995). *History of sexuality*, West Universe Publishing House, Romania.
- 3) The Government of Romania NATIONAL PROGRAM "HEALTH EDUCATION IN THE ROMANIAN SCHOOL"
https://gov.ro/fisiere/programe_fisiere/program-educatie-sanatate.pdf
- 4) Official Gazette, Law no. 272/2004 regarding the protection and promotion of children's rights